

FAIR Vocabularies For Cross Domain Data Integration - what is key?

Notes from the day one group brainstorming session.

Facilitator: Lesley Wyborn

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Today's Theme was FAIR Vocabularies For and Across domains.

CROSS DOMAIN ISSUES

We started with a keynote on "Vocabularies across Domains". We then went into 3 sessions on vocabularies within these three broad domains::

- 1) FAIR Vocabularies for Health and Biosecurity (H&B)
- 2) FAIR vocabularies for Earth and Environmental Sciences (E&ES)
- 3) FAIR vocabularies for Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences and Indigenous (HASS&I)

Discussion: What did individual domains learn from the presentations from the other domains (technology, techniques, community approaches) that can help us advance FAIR vocabs across domains?

- 1) What did Health and Biosecurity learn from E&ES And HASSI?

WorldFAIR - can we build FIPs?

But how do you still choose which is the right implementation?

- Framework of *Local > Community > Global* as a maturity model
- The need for even more detailed metadata descriptions of vocabularies as a whole
- Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM)
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- 2) What did Earth and Environmental Sciences learn from HAB and HASS&I?

How vocabs can be used/what they are used for is broader than I'd been exposed to in environment field

Looking for concepts and questions and drawing them out using analytical tools. The value of vocabs is broad - text analysis and data mining concepts provides insights

Lets just get vocabs down - from the local to global - but, we see we may develop the problem that medicine has - lots of concepts then we need to handle the mapping. Interested in ?SHOOM mapping between concepts

- 3) What did Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences and Indigenous learn from E&ES and H&B
- 4) ?

Regarding Indigenous Data - The question of legitimacy - what you do with the data and if you are the legitimate person to do that, needs to be legitimate in the eyes of the Indigenous Data holder.

Further discussion: are there any barriers that none of the domains have addressed that will hinder cross domain FAIR vocabs?

We don't have mechanisms for re-using part of vocabs - we are short on mechanisms to re-use subsets

Ability to generate PIDs at the scale we will need to

USE CASE BUILDING

Is there something practical or research topic you would like to do across multiple domains (use case), that requires FAIRer vocabs?

What are the ideal forms of infrastructure at the local, community to global

And characterising these more

Mapping different concepts of place from one domain to another - Response - 'universals' - has been identified as priorities in worldFAIR.

CODATA workshop on universals - we are establishing a set of collaborations to handle the potential for things to get hairy - eg inter-planetary communications to the social sciences.

Gazateers - extending to locations that have not been determined.

The RDA tools are being developed through the Health Commons - potential to expand, would like to see that happen into next year.

Would like to see more FIPs development

WorldFAIR CEESDA (WorldFAIR+)

How will this help advance key issues of FAIR vocabs across domains? (the positives)

What will the main challenges of this be? (the challenges)